

A global typology of cities supporting coordinated climate action

Simon Montfort^{1*}, Florian Nachtigall^{2,3}, Tim Repke², Claudia R. Binder¹,
Felix Creutzig^{2,3,4*}

¹Human-Environment Relations in Urban Systems, École polytechnique fédérale de
Lausanne, Station 2, Lausanne, 1015, Switzerland.

²Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Member of the Leibniz Association,
Telegrafenberg A 31, Potsdam, 14473, Brandenburg, Germany.

³Sustainability Economics of Human Settlements, Technical University Berlin, Straße des
17. Juni 135, Berlin, 10623, Berlin, Germany.

⁴Bennett Institute for Innovation and Policy Acceleration, Science Policy Research Unit,
University of Sussex, Sussex House, Falmer, Brighton, BN1 9RH, East Sussex, United
Kingdom.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): simon.montfort@epfl.ch; fc358@sussex.ac.uk;

Abstract

Cities are central to climate action, yet the highly local nature of urban case studies limits the generalizability of climate solutions across diverse contexts. Here, we develop a data-driven typology of 11,000 cities based on 12 structural characteristics and statistically identify four types of cities that focus on development, urban planning, mitigation, or are megacities. Linking this typology to more than 100,000 scientific case studies reveals strong regional patterns and substantial evidence gaps, particularly in cities with planning needs, despite high potentials for solution transfer learning. Using ten type- and region-representative cities, we exemplify how the typology enables systematic learning: cities with development and urban planning priorities primarily draw on adaptation and basic need solutions for water security, heat management, and resilient spatial planning; Wealthier and mature global north cities can rely more balanced solution portfolios involving, for instance, building retrofits, low-carbon mobility, and technological solutions; Megacities require coordinated, cross-sectoral strategies that combine infrastructure renewal with nature-based and socio-institutional approaches that are reflected in available solution evidence. Our typology offers a scalable basis for matching climate solutions to city needs, improving evidence synthesis, and IPCC assessments.

Keywords: cities, transfer-learning, climate solutions, IPCC

Main

All cities are different, but some are similar to each other. This poses a major challenge for urban sustainability science and for global climate assessments such as the IPCC's Special Report on Cities, which must synthesize thousands of highly local case studies into guidance relevant across diverse urban contexts [1–3]. Because urban systems operate under highly varied boundary conditions and exhibit strong contextual complexity, generalizing from individual case studies and replicating findings in other cities has proven challenging [4]. As a result, the underlying literature remains fragmented and unsystematically organized, and global assessments struggle to determine which cities can learn from one another and under what conditions [2].

39 Urban typologies provide a promising foundation for addressing this challenge. By structuring cities
40 according to shared characteristics, typologies help organize and interpret an increasingly complex
41 knowledge base [3, 5]. Yet existing approaches have important limitations. First, IPCC typologies develop
42 qualitative archetypes[6, p.920] but do not systematically connect to specific cities. Scaling such work
43 would require extensive manual expert judgement. With thousands of cities and dozens of relevant
44 socio-environmental and infrastructural dimensions, consistent expert grouping is no longer feasible.
45 Second, even existing quantitative typologies typically cover only a few hundred cities[7, 8], making them
46 inadequate for global science assessments. Third, most typologies do not link to city-specific scientific
47 evidence in ways that yield tangible examples for practitioners to learn from[3, 9]. A global data-driven
48 approach is therefore needed to capture robust patterns across all cities in a transparent and reproducible
49 manner—one that connects local evidence to global structure and identifies where climate solutions may
50 transfer across contexts, while also enabling systematic selection of representative cases for bottom-
51 up learning. Such an approach complements polycentric climate action in Ostrom’s spirit, fostering
52 experimentation and learning beyond the constraints of international climate negotiations [10].

53 Here, we address this critical research gap and develop a global typology of 11,000 global cities linked
54 to the city-specific evidence of 100,000 studies covering over 220,000 city cases (on average, 2.2 cities per
55 case study) from the largest open-source scientific database [11]. We develop a rigorous, replicable, and
56 transparent Deep Embedded Clustering ensemble pipeline that outperforms traditional algorithms [12, 13]
57 to identify groups of cities with similar structural characteristics relevant for climate action (see Methods),
58 accessible online (<https://cities-explorer.eubucco.com>). This provides the foundation for a new empirical
59 framework for evidence-based transfer learning. We demonstrate its utility by analysing over 1,000 case-
60 study abstracts across ten representative cities spanning four city types and seven world regions. The
61 typology’s robustness and interpretability are confirmed through expert assessments and quantitative
62 validation analyses (see Methods; Extended Data Fig. A1-A2). Together, the typology and the linked
63 evidence base offer a scalable and systematic underpinning for the global evidence assessments, like those
64 in the IPCC SR on cities, to inform practitioners about effective and feasible climate mitigation and
65 adaptation solutions in cities.

66 Results

67 Global typology indicates distinct challenges and climate solutions for 68 different types of cities

69 Our global typology of 11,000 cities with at least 50,000 inhabitants reveals four key city types that
70 together capture the spectrum of urban development, particularly regarding demographic scale and change,
71 socio-economic development, and biophysical energy demand conditions (Fig. 1). At one extreme are
72 low-emission cities with profound development needs (Type 1), while at the other are megacities with
73 high population density and simultaneous adaptation and mitigation pressures (Type 4). In between lie
74 economically emerging cities with high GDP growth that are horizontally expanding (Type 2) and high-
75 income cities with limited growth but strong infrastructure that vary in their climate solution needs (Table
76 1).

Fig. 1 – Overview of the typology. Global city types (a), their characteristic profiles (b), and their distribution across world regions (c). Colours denote each city’s main type; To communicate uncertainty in the assignment to the different types, we used a probability threshold to assign cities to mixed types, shown in grey. Using our online application (<https://cities-explorer.eubucco.com>) and statistical validation for the choice of a meaningful threshold, we assigned mixed types when the probabilities are below $0.65 \times$ the cluster-specific median (threshold validation in Extended Data Fig. A2). In panel (a), point size reflects population, and three representative cities per type (with the highest assignment probabilities and populations above 0.8 million) are labelled for illustration. In panel (b), cluster characteristics (for details, see methods) are shown as deviations of the type-specific medians from the global medians. All variables were percentile-normalised to ensure comparability across differently scaled measures; values therefore indicate percentage-point shifts within the global percentile distribution. For example, a value of +50 means that the median city of this type lies 50 percentile points above the global median for that variable. Panel (c) shows the representation of the four types across world regions. Filled bars indicate the share of each main type; patterned grey bars denote mixed-type cities.

77 Development priorities dominate cities of Type 1, with low human development, and infrastructure,
 78 and very high cooling needs. These cities are generally smaller in population and GDP per capita, yet
 79 face growing climate stressors and increasing cooling demands. They are mostly situated in Central
 80 America, Africa, and Southeast Asia. In Mombasa (Kenya), studies document how flooding and water

81 scarcity disproportionately affect lower-income households and informal settlements, with cascading health
 82 consequences [14–18]. While less extensively studied, cities such as Mbeya (Tanzania) exhibit similar
 83 dynamics of fast population growth combined with constrained infrastructure. Collectively, these cities
 84 are similar in their median characteristics to African cities (Fig. 2a), where 1,532 cities (13% of all cities
 85 globally) belong to this main type (Fig. 2c-d), while in Asia, the 3,060 cities of this main type (37%) are
 86 smaller, growing and densifying faster than regional peers.

Table 1 – Summary of the four global city types, their core characteristics, and overarching climate-action needs. The summary is rooted in the statistical analysis shown in Fig. 1 and 2.

Type	Characteristics and geography	Overarching mitigation and adaptation needs
Type 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smaller, lower-income cities with limited infrastructure, low human development, and high cooling needs with intermediary to fast population growth. • Predominantly in Central America, Africa, and South and Southeast Asia. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening basic services, expanding resilient water and sanitation systems, reducing exposure in informal settlements, and preparing for heat-related risks. • Upgrading infrastructure to manage future climate risks and mainstreaming climate action with development.
Type 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economically growing cities with intermediate infrastructure, low population density, and rapid horizontal expansion. • Located mainly in South/Central America, Africa, and South/Southeast Asia. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guiding spatial expansion toward compact, transit-oriented development. • Ensuring that compact urban growth is complemented by green and blue spaces to mitigate heat. • Early mitigation through compact growth, energy-efficient buildings, and clean energy access.
Type 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wealthier cities with strong infrastructure, low population and economic growth, and high per-capita emissions. • Concentrated in North America, Europe, East Asia (China/Japan), and southern South America. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deep mitigation via building retrofits, electrified transport, and densification of low-density suburbs. • Adaptation focusing on extreme heat, flood risk, and upgrading ageing infrastructure.
Type 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-density, fast-growing cities with advanced infrastructure but acute cross-sectoral pressures. • Distributed across Africa, Asia, Europe, and the Americas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated mitigation–adaptation strategies: managing development, poverty (e.g. informal settlements), expanding resilient infrastructure, reducing congestion and pollution, and scaling nature-based cooling. • Strengthened governance capacity to coordinate across sectors and balance development with decarbonization.

87 Type 2 represents economically emerging cities with intermediary infrastructure and low population
 88 density (Fig. 1b), which makes urban planning challenges acute. Mostly situated in South and Central
 89 America, Africa, South and South-East Asia (Fig. 1a), these cities are characterized by small but slightly
 90 larger populations than in Type 1, and horizontal expansion (low population density growth) (Fig. 1b).
 91 Planning deficits can amplify both vulnerability and intensify CO₂ emissions. In Abuja (Nigeria), rapid
 92 spatial expansion has transformed the built-up area from just 1.8% in 1990 to nearly 20% by 2019, driving
 93 extensive land cover change and loss of vegetation [19]. The dispersion of settlement patterns has created
 94 major challenges for sustainable land use planning, with implications for mobility, green infrastructure,
 95 and environmental sustainability. In Asia, 2,262 cities of this type (20% of the cities globally) (Fig. 2b-c)
 96 exhibit lower population and population growth than their regional medians (Fig. 2a), defining features of
 97 this type more generally (Fig. 1b). Thus, Type 2 cities combine high adaptation needs with high mitigation

98 potential, particularly through urban planning that can guide expansion toward more sustainable and
 99 compact forms.

a Difference to region-specific median

c Percentage of cities

	Africa	Asia	Australasia	Europe	North America	Small Islands	South America
Type 1	13.41%	26.79%		0.01%	0.11%	0.67%	1.61%
Type 2	2.16%	19.8%		1.58%	1.23%	0.37%	3.57%
Type 3		4.46%	0.36%	9.09%	3.33%	0.14%	0.39%
Type 4	0.29%	0.61%		0.04%	0.03%		0.05%
mixed	3.02%	4.26%	0.03%	0.33%	0.38%	0.33%	1.54%
Total	18.88%	55.93%	0.39%	11.06%	5.06%	1.51%	7.17%

d Absolute number of cities

	Africa	Asia	Australasia	Europe	North America	Small Islands	South America
Type 1	1532	3060		1	12	77	184
Type 2	247	2262		181	140	42	408
Type 3		509	41	1038	380	16	45
Type 4	33	70		5	3		6
mixed	345	487	3	38	43	38	176
Total	2157	6388	44	1263	578	173	819

Fig. 2 – Regional characterisation of clusters. Differences between each city type and its regional peers (in a). We first convert each variable to a percentile scale (1–100) so that all indicators are comparable. We then compute how far the median value of each type lies above or below the median value of all cities in the same region. Only the three variables with the largest deviations are shown. For example, a value of –50 for heating degree days in North America means that the median city of this type experiences 50 percentile points fewer heating needs than the median North American city — in other words, it sits roughly halfway lower in the regional distribution of this variable. We excluded statistics for type-region combinations with <0.05% of all cities globally for better readability. For each region-type combination, we show the percentage of the cities (b) and the absolute number of cities (c).

100 Type 3 includes wealthier cities where mitigation challenges dominate. They exhibit high per-capita
101 emissions but limited population and economic growth, with generally strong infrastructure and higher
102 levels of gender equality. Located in North America, Europe, East Asia (predominantly China and Japan),
103 and the southern parts of South America, this type ranks first in per capita CO₂ emissions (Extended
104 Data Fig. A7). These cities are often characterized by low population density. In Berlin (Germany), travel-
105 related CO₂ emissions in suburban neighborhoods are nearly twice those in denser central districts under
106 otherwise similar socio-demographic conditions [20]. In Toronto (Canada), low-density suburbs contribute
107 the most to transport-related emissions [21]. This main type is most prevalent in Europe (1038 cities; 9%
108 globally) and Asia (508 cities; 4.5% globally) (Fig. 2b). The latter have almost 20 percentile points higher
109 heating needs, lower population density, and higher cooling needs than their regional peers, characteristics
110 that are common to this type across the globe (Fig. 1b). 1.8% of the African cities in this group are mixed
111 types as they often combine larger populations and higher economic development (Fig. 1a).

112 Type 4 encompasses large and megacities, marked by high density, rapid population growth, and
113 relatively advanced infrastructure, often with compound, cross-sectoral priorities related to development,
114 urban planning, or mitigation. These cities with compound challenges are spread out across the world
115 regions. In Africa, Lagos (Nigeria) and Cairo (Egypt) combine massive population with fast growth and
116 high adaptation pressures, and extensive informal settlements that lack basic service provision and are
117 prone to climate change impacts [22, 23]. Similarly, in megacities of Asia like Mumbai (India), millions
118 of dwellers lack access to safe drinking water and sanitation [24]. Such development challenges have
119 also manifested in Coimbatore (India), where rapid economic growth has amplified pressures from waste
120 management and pollution [25–27]. Empirical studies also show increasing urban heat island intensity [28]
121 and significant potential for cool roof interventions to reduce building energy demand [29]. Resilience
122 planning documents promise ambitious futures but often fail to confront the entrenched political and
123 development practices that continue to exacerbate climate risks [30]. Meanwhile, cities like Tokyo (Japan)
124 and Seoul (South Korea) highlight how advanced economies face simultaneous adaptation and mitigation
125 pressures. In Europe, London (United Kingdom) and Paris (France) demonstrate how global megacities
126 must balance legacy infrastructure with deep decarbonization imperatives.

127 **Vast urban transfer learning potential from the scientific evidence**

128 The scientific evidence on climate change in cities is highly unevenly distributed (Fig. 2). While 7,000 Type
129 1 and 2 cities in the Global South, which face development and urban planning priorities (Figure 2c), are
130 covered by only approximately 60,000 city-specific case studies, the remaining 2,000 cities with mitigation
131 priorities mostly located in developed countries are covered by 120,000 studies (Fig. 2e) — roughly 7 times
132 as many studies per city. Yet even in better-studied regions, coverage is far from complete: 27% of the more
133 developed type 3 cities with mainly mitigation challenges are not represented in any city-specific study,
134 and among megacities with cross-cutting challenges, 24% remain unstudied. For cities where development
135 and urban planning priorities dominate (types 1-2), the research gap is huge: 69% and 53% of these cities,
136 respectively, are not covered by any case study. These disparities are not merely academic; they signify a
137 critical gap in evidence-based policy guidance for the majority of the global urban population.

Fig. 3 – Evidence-based learning potential per group. Colours indicate the main city types identified through the ensemble Deep Embedded Clustering pipeline; dot size reflects the number of city-specific case studies (a). The similarity to all other cities captures the mean similarity in scaled feature space among the covariates used for the clustering (in b) and to those cities with at least one study (in c). Lighter colours denote greater similarity. Together with cities not covered by any study by type (in d) and as a count (in e), this captures the extent to which cities may draw on scientific evidence generated elsewhere or where targeted new evidence is required. Barcharts by city type display the distribution of city cases studied (e), the similarity to all cities (f), the similarity to cities with at least one study (g), and the number of cities alongside the proportion of cities with and without case studies (h). City-specific case studies were identified using a keyword-matching, unsupervised geoparsing approach (for details, see methods).

138 Importantly, this uneven distribution has profound implications for global learning. Our analysis shows
 139 that many under-researched cities, particularly in East Asia and South America, are highly similar to other
 140 cities that are covered by research (Fig. 2c) while targetted new studies in Africa where critical research
 141 gaps persist for cities with development needs (Fig. 2d-e) could yield vast learning potentials as cities
 142 are similar to many others (Fig. 2b). This suggests a substantial untapped potential for evidence-based
 143 transfer learning, whereby solutions tested elsewhere could be adapted and scaled to local contexts.

144 Exemplifying cities’ transfer-learning potential from evidence-based climate 145 solutions

146 We demonstrate how our data-driven typology enables evidence-based learning from climate solutions
 147 documented in case study literature and systematic identification of critical evidence gaps that correspond
 148 with cities’ needs. To do so, we selected ten cities covering all four types and seven IPCC world regions.

149 Three of the selected cities lie in Asia, reflecting that the largest urban population share is from that
 150 continent. Using over 50 solution categories relevant for the IPCC, we annotated 1,011 article abstracts
 151 to synthesize climate solutions in cities across the four types (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4 – City case study climate solution examples to learn from. Cities are coloured according to their main type in the data-driven typology. The ten cities for which we manually screened case studies for the presence of climate solutions are shown in darker colour tones. Cities displayed in lighter tones represent structurally similar cities that serve as learning candidates for the climate solutions documented in the ten selected case-study cities. Our deep embedded clustering (DEC) ensemble pipeline produces, for every city, a probability distribution of belonging to each type (for details, see Methods). Its main types are determined by the largest probability. Consistent with the results from our typology, we identify learning candidates by computing cosine similarity between these probability profiles: cities with a high similarity score share structural characteristics with the corresponding case-study city. For each of the ten case-study examples, we selected the three most similar cities to illustrate the learning potential and ensure diversity. This results in a total of 40 cities shown in the map (10 case-study cities and 30 learning candidates).

152 The solutions in many of the small to medium-sized cities, which tend to be more prevalent in type
 153 1 and type 2, are relatively narrowly concentrated on specific services and solution types. While thermal
 154 comfort and heat stress management are prevalent across most cities, mobility and building solutions,
 155 particularly focused on mitigation, are more prevalent in relatively mature cities (mainly Type 3 cities:
 156 Louisville, Berlin, and Melbourne, with mitigation priorities, and to a lesser extent, Type 4 Chongqing,
 157 illustrating cross-cutting challenges of megacities in that type). Solutions related to basic needs and
 158 adaptation are more prevalent in poorer cities (mainly Type 1 Cartagena and Mombasa, and Type 2
 159 Cancun and Makassar). These focus particularly on water and disaster risk management.

160 ***Type 1 cities with development priorities may learn from adaptation solutions for water***
 161 ***services.***

162 Cities in this group (e.g., Cartagena, Mombasa) face basic development constraints—low GDP per
 163 capita, limited infrastructure, and rapidly expanding populations. Their climate research coverage is
 164 sparse, yet where available, it concentrates on adaptation (68% of all solutions identified; Extended Data
 165 Fig. A6) addressing water access, disaster management, and thermal comfort (Fig. 5). For instance, in
 166 Mombasa (Kenya), climate responses are strongly adaptation-focused. Water-sensitive urban planning and

167 community-driven flood infrastructure (e.g., wetland restoration, elevated roads) have been promoted to
168 address recurrent inundation and poor drainage [16, 31]. The Lafarge Ecosystems Programme demonstrates
169 how partnerships between municipal authorities, businesses, and local communities deliver “soft
170 engineering” resilience via nature-based solutions through urban greening and mangrove rehabilitation
171 [32, 33]. Yet institutional fragmentation and limited municipal capacity hinder integration of such efforts
172 into broader economic development and urban planning frameworks [34]. Cartagena (Colombia) similarly
173 exemplifies the developmental transition challenge—combining flood vulnerability with tourism-driven
174 growth and an ageing building stock. Here, the literature points to participatory planning as an enabling
175 factor for heritage-sensitive retrofitting for efficiency increases in building envelopes as pathways to
176 balance adaptation and equity goals (Fig. 5). Proposed solutions include thermoacoustic roofing materials
177 reducing household emissions by up to 5.8% compared to asbestos–cement alternatives[35], participatory
178 flood management[36] via urban reservoirs[37], and blue–green roof modules for decentralized water
179 harvesting[38].

180 ***Type 2 illustrates learning from adaptation-focussed solutions and a widening set of***
181 ***cross-cutting solutions***

182 Type 2 cities such as Santiago de Cuba (Cuba), Cancún (Mexico), and Basra (Iraq). These cities are
183 characterised by modest economic development and increasing exposure to climate extremes. For cities
184 with main type 2, the evidence base remains relatively sparse. In such cases, evidence-based learning may
185 turn to other similar cities. In this case, Makassar, which shares membership between Type 4 (42% cluster
186 membership with mega cities with compound challenges) and Type 2 (34% membership), can provide
187 insights on lessons learnt. Makassar provides one of the richest empirical bases, with over 50 studies
188 documenting adaptation pathways across informal settlements [39–41, 41–44] (Fig. 5). Nature-based
189 solutions—green infrastructure, urban forestry, and blue–green corridors (Fig. 5)—are central to flood and
190 heat management, but their implementation is often constrained by land-use conflicts and unclear tenure
191 [43]. Participatory co-design has been critical in overcoming these barriers, while coordinated planning
192 of green areas within redevelopment schemes could lower local heat islands by up to 9.2 °C in formal
193 and 6.3 °C in informal areas [41]. Complementary studies highlight early-warning systems for floods [45],
194 integrated drainage and risk-sensitive housing, and community-based disaster governance [46, 47]. Cancún
195 (Mexico), by contrast, exemplifies a tourism-dependent city facing dual challenges of flood exposure and
196 emission reduction, and only one study contains solutions on access to social protection for vulnerable and
197 informal residents (Fig. 5).

198 For Type 2 cities, the central insight lies in integrating adaptation and spatial planning. Experience from
199 Makassar shows that participatory governance can accelerate implementation of blue–green infrastructure
200 and smart risk management technologies—pathways that other fast-growing, under-researched cities could
201 emulate.

202 ***Type 3 cities exemplifying mitigation needs may learn from diversified solution portfolios***

203 Type 3 cities—such as Berlin (Germany), Melbourne (Australia), and Louisville (USA)—are wealthier,
204 slower-growing, and largely have mitigation priorities (Fig. 1 and Extended Data Fig. A3 for these
205 specific cities). Here, documented solutions are most abundant (262 in Melbourne, 211 in Berlin, and

Fig. 5 – Evidence on specific climate solutions covered in the scientific literature of the different exemplary case study cities. Numbers and colour fills indicate the number of studies on each specific climate solution (on the vertical axis) for the exemplary case study cities (on the horizontal axis) grouped by service/provision sector. For details on annotation rules for the manual identification of climate solutions from the literature, see Supplementary Materials, Tables 2-3.

206 9 in Louisville), with solutions distributed more evenly across adaptation (32%), mitigation (36%), and
 207 cross-cutting solutions (32%) (Extended Data Fig. A6). In Berlin, the literature covers a wide array of
 208 infrastructure renewal efforts—building retrofits, efficient district heating, and sustainable mobility. Over
 209 a quarter of studies focus on low-carbon mobility (26%) and thermal comfort (31%), reflecting the city’s
 210 sprawling form (see population density and low population density growth in Extended Data Fig. A3g)
 211 and growing heat stress. Melbourne similarly illustrates the importance of infrastructure renewal and
 212 citizen engagement. Its extensive coverage (180 studies) reflects decades of urban heat adaptation, with
 213 green infrastructure and heat-stress management comprising nearly 40% of the city’s climate literature.
 214 Technological uptake—smart energy systems, building automation, and electric transport—complements
 215 broader socio-cultural change toward sustainable lifestyles and governance reforms. Louisville represents
 216 a smaller but instructive case, where the literature concentrates on mitigating urban heat through tree-
 217 planting and urban form interventions, revealing how smaller cities can draw from lessons of larger
 218 metropolitan peers.

219 For Type 3 cities, the transferable insight lies in integrated socio-technical transitions: infrastructure
220 renewal alone is insufficient to reduce emissions in developed cities without cultural acceptance,
221 participatory governance, and behavioural shifts.

222 *Type 4 — Megacities with Cross-Cutting Challenges: Systemic Integration*

223 Type 4 cities—such as Chongqing (China)—face the most complex blend of adaptation and mitigation
224 pressures. They are economically dynamic, densely populated, and exposed to simultaneous heat and flood
225 stress, with strong energy demand growth. Research coverage in many of the cities in this type is relatively
226 high and thematically diverse. In Chongqing, studies document large-scale infrastructural interventions
227 (e.g., sponge-city flood management, carbon removal zones) alongside efforts to build social awareness
228 and risk governance capacity. The evidence also underscores learning potential from district heating and
229 cooling, compact mobility systems, and nature-based measures for disaster reduction (Fig. 5). These cities
230 often share membership with other types as they are spread out across the world, embedded in varying
231 contexts, but united by mostly large and fast-growing populations, high population density, and high
232 critical infrastructure (Fig. 1).

233 Discussion

234 We present a global data-driven typology of 11,000 cities linked to more than 100,000 case studies
235 on climate-change mitigation and adaptation. We show that many under-researched, fast-growing cities
236 resemble cities for which extensive evidence already exists, opening new opportunities for evidence-based
237 transfer of climate solutions. We use this typology to develop an empirical framework for identifying when
238 and how solutions can be transferred across cities, and we illustrate its application by analysing over 1,000
239 case-study abstracts from ten representative cities across four types and seven world regions.

240 Our data-driven approach complements qualitative archetype typologies. While archetypes used in
241 the IPCC Assessment Report 6 offer valuable conceptual foundations[6, p.920], recommendations for
242 mitigation through spatial planning, electrification, urban green-blue infrastructure, and socio-behavioural
243 aspects are not rooted in the socio-environmental and infrastructural dimensions relevant for cities. By
244 contrast, our validated data-driven method identifies dominant patterns across more than 11,000 cities in
245 a systematic and reproducible way, transforming typologies into operational tools that allow connecting
246 theorization on urban development with recommendations on solution needs and transferability rooted in
247 the realities of cities rooted in indicators.

248 Our typology serves at least three critical purposes that are of interest to the broader research
249 community, the science assessments like those by the IPCC, and city practitioners. First, our typology
250 allows contextualising the many highly local and, to date, unorganised case studies that have made tracking
251 the climate solutions difficult. Utilizing our typology, researchers can understand where evidence is missing,
252 considering the evidence available in similar cities. Our typology and database can underpin systematic
253 reviews and meta-analyses aimed at evaluating the effectiveness and feasibility of climate solutions across
254 different city types. Such work can also assess study quality and synthesize findings quantitatively to
255 determine which solutions consistently reduce emissions or climate risks and in which types of cities they
256 can be reliably transferred.

257 Second, our typology provides a critical underpinning for the IPCC SR on Cities, which is tasked
258 with reviewing climate solutions for different types of cities. Our typology enables a more thorough
259 understanding of which contextual factors enable effective climate solutions. This provides the backbone
260 for the next generation of urban evidence synthesis studies, as many of them do not sufficiently embrace
261 the different city types, for instance, regarding urban form interventions[48], land expansion[49], energy
262 savings[48, 50], nature-based solutions[51], or densification[52]. For expert reviews, like those by the IPCC,
263 our typology with city-specific evidence attached, contributes to making the case study selection more
264 systematic. Our database allows fast access to the relevant evidence base and selection of representative
265 cities from different city types. As such, our typology provides a basis for balancing globally valid insights
266 with locally relevant policy recommendations – critical to enhance the usefulness of science assessments
267 for policy makers[53].

268 Third, our evidence-based learning framework shows how the large and uneven body of existing urban
269 evidence can be used more systematically to identify what cities can learn from each other. In doing so, we
270 contribute to the conceptually dominated research on city learning and experimentation [10]. The typology
271 provides a structure for identifying lessons learnt from the solutions that are documented in city case
272 studies around the world. As such, our study addresses a longstanding challenge for urban climate action
273 to balance local specificity and globally relevant, generalisable insights from the thousands of city-specific
274 case studies[3, 5] and will provide researchers, decision-makers, and the IPCC with actionable guidance
275 on what climate solutions are likely feasible and can effectively reduce emissions in their specific city.

276 **Methods & Data**

277 Our three-step approach uses machine learning to assess cross-city learning potentials based on the
278 scientific evidence. First, we build a data-driven global typology of cities using deep embedded clustering
279 (a machine-learning method that groups cities with similar characteristics). In the second step, we use
280 this typology with established systematic literature-mapping methods to provide broad global knowledge
281 on climate solutions and common adaptation and mitigation challenges from local case studies on
282 representative cities [3, 5]. Systematic maps and evidence gap maps organize studies to make existing
283 research more accessible (see, e.g. [3, 54–56]) following transparent and rigorous approaches [57–59]. We
284 differentiate the literature by research location (which cities are covered), method (city-specific case study
285 or non-city-specific study), and time (when a study was published). The location-attribution builds on
286 prior work using automated geoparsing from text [3]. In the third step, we combine the previous two steps.
287 This allows us to paint a granular picture of the evidence landscape and show i) how many studies cover
288 the different city types, ii) which specific cities are well covered in the research landscape, and iii) where
289 evidence gaps exist.

290 Overall, our knowledge base offers fast and structured access to the scientific evidence on cities and
291 climate change. It can help the IPCC community and other decision-makers synthesize the range of climate
292 solutions, understand the conditions under which these solutions are effective, and guide the systematic
293 selection of city case studies across different contexts. More broadly, it lays the groundwork for bridging
294 local and global knowledge, identifying where evidence is strong or weak, and exploring how lessons from
295 well-studied cities can inform strategies in cities with less available evidence using tenable case examples.

296 **Step1: Developing a global typology of cities**

297 *City characteristics: input data for the clustering*

298 Our analysis is based on the Global Human Settlement Layer Urban Centre R2024A Database (GHSL-
299 UCDB) [60],¹ an established source for standardized global urban data which is also used by many
300 international organizations and for science assessments, such as those by the UN, including the ongoing
301 IPCC Special Report on Cities. The GHSL is based on a globally consistent spatial boundary of areas
302 with more than 50,000 inhabitants in continuous grid cells with 0.01° resolution ($\sim 1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$)—thereby
303 avoiding biases and problems with inconsistent and heterogeneous administrative definitions. Overall, the
304 GHSL-UCDB R2024A dataset offers a very comprehensive set of harmonized and integrated indicators to
305 characterize over 11,000 cities worldwide.

306 We selected a parsimonious yet representative set of indicators capturing structural determinants
307 of urban climate action in three broad dimensions that condition both mitigation and adaptation
308 potential: First, demographic scale and change (population, population density, growth rates) determine
309 the magnitude and speed of urban service demand, infrastructure expansion, and potential future exposure.
310 Second, socioeconomic and institutional capacity (GDP per capita, GDP growth, human development,
311 gender equity, and critical infrastructure) shape a city’s ability to design, finance, and implement climate
312 solutions. Third, biophysical energy demand conditions (heating and cooling degree days) drive baseline

¹https://human-settlement.emergency.copernicus.eu/ghs_ucdb_2024.php

Table 2 – Operationalization of the cities’ characteristics used in for the development of the global city typology

Variable name	Measurement	Data timescale	Data source
Population	million inhabitants	2025	GHSL
Population growth	Yearly % population growth (CAGR)	2000-2025	GHSL
Population density	Million inhabitants per km ² built-up area	2015	GHSL
Population density growth	Yearly % population density growth (CAGR)	2000-2025	GHSL
Population age	Ratio between population share under 18 and above 65	2025	GHSL
Human development index	Index between 0-1	2020	GHSL
Gender index	Index between 0-1	2020	GHSL
GDP	GPD p.c. purchased power parity in 1,000\$	2025	GHSL
GDP growth	Yearly % GDP p.c. growth (CAGR)	2000-2025	GHSL
Critical Infrastructure Index	Sum of the CISI score by urban center, normalized by the maximum value for all urban centers	2020	GHSL
Heating Degree Days	Cumulative daily average temperature deviation below 18 °C	2016	Lizana et al., 2024 [61]
Cooling Degree Days	Cumulative daily average temperature deviation above 18 °C	2016	Lizana et al., 2024 [61]

GHSL: Global Human Settlement Layer; GDP: Gross Domestic Product

energy needs, hazard sensitivities, and the relevance of particular interventions. The heating and cooling degree data were integrated from an external high-quality global gridded dataset with 0.01° resolution ($\sim 1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$) [61]. We inferred missing data for 15 coastal cities from the respective nearest city at the same latitude, as these are very likely to have very similar heating and cooling degree days. For the population age, human development index, and the female gender index, we imputed 3, 155, and 218 missing values, respectively, using k-nearest neighbour method. Before clustering, all features were standardized to a zero mean and unit variance to ensure equal contribution during model training.

The selection reflects indicators that are globally available with limited missing data, harmonized, and comparable, enabling clustering across a large and diverse set of cities. The variables were chosen to (i) represent core dimensions relevant for urban climate mitigation and adaptation; (ii) avoid highly collinear or redundant features that would obscure cluster interpretation; and (iii) ensure that the resulting typology remains interpretable and actionable for global assessments and practitioners. Thus, we construct a generic structural typology that captures foundational characteristics that share relevance across climate solutions, allowing for solution-specific insights using the case study literature linked to the cities for more in-depth, evidence-based insights.

We intentionally excluded outcome variables such as greenhouse gas emissions, hazard exposure, and vulnerability metrics from the clustering process. Following established conceptual frameworks [62], these metrics are treated as outcomes of underlying urban structure, rather than defining features of city types. Including them as clustering inputs would risk circular reasoning when later assessing how emissions or vulnerabilities vary across the identified types.

333 *Deep embedded clustering (DEC).*

We use Deep Embedded Clustering (DEC), an advanced unsupervised machine-learning technique that projects data into a low-dimensional space and iteratively refines cluster assignments [12]. First, DEC reduces the dimensionality of the raw input data (for example, city indicators) into a lower dimension. This projection effectively ‘compresses’ the information into a less detailed representation, which makes

high-level patterns more apparent and helps to produce more compact and meaningful clusters. This is particularly important for datasets with complex, nonlinear structures and latent heterogeneity—such as global urban data—where traditional clustering on raw feature space distances could fail to capture meaningful similarity between observations.

Clustering uses these representations to assign each city to a single cluster or a distribution of clusters. However, initialisation of the clustering algorithm can have an impact on the final cluster assignment. To mitigate instable outcomes and ensure robust cluster assignments, we perform multiple clusterings with different parameters and initialisations, so-called ensemble clustering [63–65], to ensure that the result is not just a random artefact of the algorithm but represents stable patterns. By aligning the results from the different clustering runs, we determine the final assignment as described below in more detail. We also compared the performance of our ensemble DEC pipeline to more traditional methods, namely simple K-Means, K-Means on the latent space, and hierarchical clustering (see Extended Data Figure A1-A2). The latter are commonly used clustering methods in geographic, economic, and climate change research [66–68]. Our results demonstrate substantial performance gains of our DEC pipeline in comparison to more traditional methods in terms of cluster separability (see Extended Data Figure A2), which confirms established findings in the literature [12, 69]. The following paragraphs offer additional details on implementation.

Unlike traditional clustering methods that operate directly in the original feature space, DEC uses an autoencoder to learn latent representations, also known as embeddings. This process involves three key components: training the autoencoder, then fitting an added clustering layer, and finally refining assignments by reducing cluster overlaps [12].

First, we trained an autoencoder, a neural network that transforms the input data (the city characteristics) into a lower-dimensional vector representation. We identified the optimal autoencoder architecture using hyperband hyperparameter tuning [70] to determine the best number of hidden units in two intermediate layers (32–96 for the first layer, and 16–32 units for the second layer), latent dimensionality (2–4), and L2 regularization strength. We kept the model architecture intentionally shallow, given that we have 12 variables and 11k observations. The encoder consists of two ReLU-activated dense layers followed by a bottleneck layer, which is mirrored by the decoder, which aims to reconstruct the input during training. Training is performed using the Adam optimizer with mean squared error loss. A 20% validation split and early stopping (patience = 10) were used to prevent overfitting. The best hyperparameters included four encoding dimensions, l2 regularization of 5.086267866771555e-06, 80 units for the first layer, and 16 units for the second layer.

Second, the learned embeddings are passed to a trainable clustering layer that performs soft assignment. This means that rather than assigning each city to only one cluster (hard assignment), we instead get a probability distribution indicating how well each cluster describes this city (soft assignment). Cluster assignment probabilities are computed using Student’s t-distribution, which measures similarity between embeddings and cluster centroids using

$$q_{ij} = \frac{(1 + |z_i - \mu_j|^2/\alpha)^{-\frac{\alpha+1}{2}}}{\sum_{j'} (1 + |z_i - \mu_{j'}|^2/\alpha)^{-\frac{\alpha+1}{2}}},$$

370 where z_i is the embedding of the i -th data point, μ_j is the centroid of cluster j , and α are the degrees
371 of freedom (set to 1 in our analysis) [12]. The resulting scores are normalized across clusters to yield soft
372 assignment probabilities. The cluster centroid is defined by the mean of all embeddings weighted by the
373 respective cluster assignment scores. Following the DEC algorithm [12], we pre-initialized cluster centroids
374 using K-Means with 20 restarts to ensure a stable, high-quality clustering and to improve convergence.

Third, cluster assignments are refined by minimising the pairwise Kullback-Leibler-divergence (KL)
between the target distributions p_{ij} and cluster assignments q_{ij} [12]. The target distribution and the
KL-divergence are defined as

$$p_{ij} = \frac{q_{ij}^2 / \sum_i q_{ij}}{\sum_{j'} (q_{ij'}^2 / \sum_i q_{ij'})}, \quad \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}} = \sum_i \sum_j p_{ij} \log \left(\frac{p_{ij}}{q_{ij}} \right).$$

375 This effectively increases the distance between clusters' centroids, improving the separability of clusters,
376 sharpening the soft cluster assignment q_{ij} , and encouraging the model to produce more confident and
377 discrete cluster assignments [12].

378 To prevent overfitting to potentially unstable pseudo-labels during refinement and to improve the
379 stability of cluster assignments, we implement an early stopping criterion based on the convergence
380 of cluster assignments. This not only acts as a form of regularization but also significantly reduces
381 computation time by avoiding unnecessary updates once the solution has stabilized. Such a convergence
382 criterion aligns with standard clustering practices [71, 72], where training halts once assignment changes
383 become minimal. We base our convergence criterion on the change of silhouette scores (threshold $< 10^{-3}$),
384 cluster assignment stability (threshold $5 \times < 10^{-3}$), and cluster centroid drift (threshold $< 10^{-3}$). The
385 silhouette score is a commonly used cluster quality score; the assignment stability is measured by the
386 proportion of cities that are re-assigned to other clusters at each step, and the drift is how far cluster
387 centroids move at each step.

388 ***Ensemble clustering.***

389 To ensure stable clustering results, we adopt an ensemble clustering strategy that runs multiple DEC
390 models, aligns their outputs, and aggregates the cluster assignments [63–65, 73–75]. This approach
391 improves the stability and robustness of the final clusters and additionally enables quantification of
392 clustering uncertainty: by examining how consistently each city is assigned to a given cluster across the
393 ensemble, we derive probabilistic membership scores that reflect confidence in each city's type. These
394 probabilities provide a principled basis for identifying which cities do not belong to one type only, i.e. are
395 mixed-type cities and for interpreting the strength of cluster assignments in downstream analyses. Our
396 ensemble involves the following steps.

397 In a first step, we match similar clusters across runs using the so-called *Hungarian algorithm* [76–79].
398 Using the confusion matrix of cluster assignments across the runs, it finds the optimal one-to-one mapping
399 by maximizing agreements across the runs. This matching is repeated until adding more clusterings
400 does not change the final result, meaning a globally stable solution is found. The stability is quantified
401 by evidence accumulation clustering (EAC) [64, 80] using the adjusted Rand index (ARI) to measure
402 similarity between successive consensus solutions. Our results show that we reach a stable solution after

403 approximately 30 runs, indicating that the 50 runs we include are sufficient for stable results (see Extended
404 Data Figure A2b). The final cluster assignments are computed based on the maximum-probability cluster.
405 We use hard assignments because the soft assignment probabilities from individual runs are not necessarily
406 comparable across the runs. This provides both a consensus label and a measure of how well each city fits
407 a given cluster. We excluded runs with less than 10 members per cluster as these represent outlier results.

408 *Evaluation and choice of number of clusters.*

409 To determine the appropriate number of clusters k and find the best clustering algorithm, we evaluated
410 clusterings with $k \in \{3, \dots, 11\}$ using three internal validation indices: i) the Silhouette coefficient, which
411 measures how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to other clusters (higher is better, range
412 -1 to 1); ii) the Calinski–Harabasz index, which evaluates cluster separation and compactness (higher is
413 better, minimum is 0); and iii) the Davies–Bouldin index, which measures the average similarity between
414 each cluster and its most similar one (lower is better, minimum is 0). Across all experiments (see Extended
415 Data Fig. A1), our DEC pipeline outperformed baseline methods (K-Means on the latent space, simple
416 K-Means, and hierarchical clustering).

417 Following these results, the number of clusters $k = 3$ would be optimal. However, our manual inspection
418 revealed that megacities were merged into other clusters, reducing interpretability and obscuring important
419 urban heterogeneity. To balance statistical quality with substantive interpretability, we choose $k = 4$. This
420 slightly decreases the internal validation indices but better preserves the distinctiveness of megacities.

421 *Validation of the typology and uncertainty.*

422 We triangulate three different approaches to validate the typology. First, we used our interactive web
423 application to inspect and iteratively refine the results of our typology (<https://cities-explorer.eubucco.com>).
424 Using examples, we checked whether the cities’ characteristics match the overall properties of
425 the group they were assigned to, vis-à-vis the other groups’ characteristics. To quantify the uncertainty
426 in our assignments, because cities can share challenges that span across types due to the continuous,
427 highly complex urban characteristics that do not always reflect only one main type, we assign cities to
428 mixed types based on the cluster-specific distribution of probabilities. We assigned mixed types when
429 the probabilities are below $0.65 \times$ the cluster-specific median (threshold validation in Extended Data
430 Fig. A3). Second, we used quantitative clustering quality metrics (Extended Data Fig. A2). These
431 quality metrics showed that our DEC ensemble pipeline, besides providing advantages for uncertainty
432 communication with the assignment probabilities, performs considerably better than more traditional
433 methods against which we benchmarked our results. Third, to ensure that the quantitative performance
434 metrics also capture substantively meaningful improvements that matter in our domain, namely, outcomes
435 related to emissions, vulnerability, and health, following established approaches in the literature[62], we
436 computed ANOVA percentage of variation accounted for by the different clustering approaches. Our results
437 indicate substantial and substantive improvements in our DEC pipeline, compared to traditional methods
438 (Extended Data Fig. A1). This shows that the cluster assignment refinements of our more advanced
439 method indeed translate into meaningful improvements.

440 ***Attribution of cities to IPCC regions.***

441 We assign each city in the GHSL-UCDB 2024 to an Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)
442 Working Group II continental region that contains the polygon center of that city. We used the official
443 shapefiles from AR6² to outline seven world regions: North America, South America, Europe, Africa, Asia,
444 Australia, and Small Island States. Some cities could not be matched to an IPCC region due to missing
445 or low-resolution coastal boundary data, particularly in Small Island States. In these cases, we choose the
446 closest region that is within a 15km boundary from the centroid. For cities matched to multiple regions, we
447 manually resolved ambiguities. Any remaining unmatched cities are manually assigned to a region based
448 on their geographic location and country context.

449 The IPCC does not provide explicit definitions of Small (sovereign) Island States and Small (non-
450 sovereign) Islands. AR6 Chapter 15 on Small Islands simply refers to their isolation, dependency on
451 trade and resources, and their vulnerability to climate change. To this end, we derive reproducible
452 definitions. Following related work [81, 82], we capture small non-sovereign islands using their geographic
453 size (below 5,000 km²) and distance-based isolation (more than 10 km from any other non-small island
454 or the continental mainland) using high-resolution island databases [83]. We manually validated the
455 classifications, which confirmed the much higher quality of the assignments based on the high-resolution
456 islands database [83]. We excluded two cities in Myanmar and six in Bangladesh due to errors in the
457 shapefiles. Overall, we identified 173 cities on Small Islands. Additionally, we identified 39 Small Island
458 States using the established definition of the United Nations³.

459 **Step 2: Systematic mapping and reviewing methods to identify**
460 **evidence-based climate solutions**

461 We queried OpenAlex, the largest open source database of scientific literature, covering 93% of the
462 literature cited in the recent sixth assessment report by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
463 (IPCC) [3] and added missing abstracts from Web of Science and Scopus. After deduplication, we identify
464 more than 100,000 case studies on climate change and cities using a keyword match augmented geoparser.

465 ***Query development.***

466 We updated and extended the database from Montfort et al. [3] to identify studies on climate change and
467 cities. This update uses a refined OpenAlex query to ensure our search results are the most comprehensive.
468 Results should cover climate change and urban systems or broader climate-related topics that do not
469 directly reference climate change (e.g., nature-based solutions, adaptive capacity). We iteratively adjusted
470 the query terms, each time checking that 35 known-relevant papers (see Supplementary materials Table 1)
471 are captured by our query (high recall) while not being overly inclusive (low precision). Two articles from
472 our reference dataset were not captured due to missing abstracts, indicating our queries exceed a 94% recall.
473 Our final queries are listed in Table A1 and consist of combinations of urban keywords and a thematic
474 focus, namely mitigation strategies, greenhouse gas (GHG) dynamics, carbon dioxide removal, and climate
475 impacts and adaptation. In total, we retrieved nearly 250,000 works published before 24.03.2025 (retrieved
476 22.04.2025) from OpenAlex.

²<https://github.com/SantanderMetGroup/ATLAS>

³<https://www.un.org/ohrls/content/about-small-island-developing-states>

477 ***Additional missing abstracts retrieved from Web of Science and Scopus.***

478 Due to copyright claims by some publishers, OpenAlex has to withhold the abstracts for about 20,000
479 records in the API. To this end, we supplement missing abstracts using Scopus and Web of Science (WoS)
480 based on their DOIs. Since DOIs do not always uniquely identify a paper, we ensure that titles match
481 closely with the one in the OpenAlex record (Jaro-Winkler distance < 0.2). This process adds more than
482 10,000 abstracts from Scopus and 140 from WoS, reducing the proportion of missing abstracts to 4.4%.

483 ***De-duplication.***

484 Overall, we retrieved 254,161 unique OpenAlex records, of which 11,208 are missing an abstract, and 339
485 are missing titles after gap-filling. OpenAlex tracks all versions of a publication as separate records, for
486 example, the pre-print and final article. For this work, we only want to retain a single record in these cases
487 and need further de-duplication to avoid double-counting the same articles. To do so, we use SemHash,
488 which encodes publication text into embeddings using the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 SentenceTransformer and
489 measures pairwise similarities between these embeddings. After merging records below a set threshold, our
490 final dataset is reduced by 9.81% to just over 230,000 studies.

491 ***Case study identification.***

492 We then identified the case studies used in this analysis, following the procedure developed and validated
493 by Montfort et al. [3]. This procedure combines two different approaches: a simple search for city names
494 and the geoparser Mordecai3 [84]. Mordecai3 identifies geographic locations using a transformer-based
495 named entity recognizer and links results to the geographic names database.⁴ The keyword-matching
496 approach searches over 11,000 city names from the GHSL-UCDB 2024A [85]. Ambiguous city names are
497 resolved using country keywords when present. In the absence of country information, the assignment is
498 randomised using observed probabilities derived from prior publications.

499 Both approaches incorporate rigorous data cleaning to reduce false positives, including removal of
500 misleading patterns such as references to international agreements, parenthetical citations, and text
501 following acknowledgements or references. Special characters in city names are standardized to improve
502 matching accuracy.

503 Each method has specific strengths: named entity recognition captures locations at multiple scales,
504 including subunits, like train stations inside a city, but may misattribute when subunits, like substates,
505 share coordinates with cities; keyword matching avoids this but cannot resolve intra-city locations. We
506 empirically validated each method individually and in combination. Cities were considered identified
507 if predicted by the geoparser alone, the keyword approach alone, both methods simultaneously, or
508 either method independently. Further technical details and validation procedures are provided in
509 Montfort et al. [3], particularly Extended Data Fig. A7.

510 From the 230,000 records, more than 100,000 contain at least one geographic location that we can
511 match to a region as described above.

⁴<https://www.geonames.org/>

512 **Step 3: Linking the Urban Typology to the Systematic Mapping of the Urban** 513 **Case Studies**

514 *Case study database.*

515 By linking the global typology of cities (Step 1) with the city-specific case studies in the scientific evidence
516 landscape (Step 2), we generated a unique database that provides fast access to relevant literature. This
517 literature is searchable, for instance, by city type, world region, and publication year in a pre-processed
518 form, reducing the time required for researchers and IPCC experts to access relevant evidence and allows
519 for a systematic selection of urban case studies.

520 The database is structured in an Excel file containing four interconnected sheets:

- 521 • **Overview:** Explains how to use the database, e.g., how to search using the customizable filter and the
522 variables that the different sheets contain.
- 523 • **City Clustering Data:** Includes over 11,000 cities used in the clustering exercise for typology
524 development, providing the foundation for identifying global patterns and grouping cities based on
525 relevant criteria.
- 526 • **Case Study Database:** Comprises over 100,000 case studies attributed to cities, each with metadata
527 including city name, abstract, citations, and a URL to the full text (where available).

528 The database allows users to filter entries by key columns (e.g., city name, abstract) to efficiently
529 identify relevant studies. This functionality enables targeted searches for literature that informs both
530 the typology and detailed case analyses. For instance, filtering abstracts for terms such as “climate” or
531 “sustainability” allows the extraction of studies relevant to specific thematic or policy areas. We anticipate
532 that this database will significantly facilitate the work of IPCC experts.

533 *Analysis of the learning potential based on 10 exemplary city cases and associated* 534 *city-specific case studies.*

535 To illustrate the cross-city transfer learning from climate solutions, we selected 10 cities from our typology
536 while balancing regional representation (seven IPCC regions: North America, South America, Europe,
537 Africa, Asia, Oceania, and Small islands) with recognisability, and the number of studies to annotate. All
538 four types and seven world regions are represented in our selection. For recognisability of the cities and
539 illustrative purposes, we tended to select larger cities than average to ensure sufficient research coverage
540 to illustrate the learning potential for other similar cities from the ten selected cities that we analysed.

541 To limit the effort needed to analyse the data, we selected single-city case studies that were consistently
542 identified as city-specific case studies by both the spatial intersection approach and the keyword matching
543 approach (for details, see methods, section 4).

544 In a group effort, we then labelled the article abstracts in a online annotation platform [86]. First, we
545 determined whether an article’s abstract was relevant, i.e., whether it covered any climate solutions, and
546 then we decided which of the over 50 climate solutions (s) to assign.

547 **Declarations**

548 **Conflict of interest/Competing interests**

549 The author declares that no conflicts of interest exist.

550 **Ethics approval**

551 Not applicable.

552 **Availability of data and materials/Code availability**

553 All replication materials and data can be found on <https://github.com/SimonMontfort/cities-learning-dec>.

554 **References**

- 555 [1] Acuto, M., Parnell, S. & Seto, K. C. Building a global urban science. *Nature Sustainability* **1**, 2–4
556 (2018).
- 557 [2] Creutzig, F. *et al.* Upscaling urban data science for global climate solutions. *Global Sustainability* **2**,
558 e2 (2019).
- 559 [3] Montfort, S. *et al.* Systematic global stocktake of over 50,000 urban climate change studies. *Nature*
560 *Cities* 1–13 (2025).
- 561 [4] Sudmant, A., Creutzig, F. & Mi, Z. Replicate and generalize to make urban research coherent.
562 *International Journal of Urban Sciences* **29**, 582–603 (2025).
- 563 [5] Creutzig, F. *et al.* Bridging the scale between the local particular and the global universal in climate
564 change assessments of cities. *Nature Cities* 1–10 (2025).
- 565 [6] Lwasa, S. *et al.* Urban systems and other settlements (2022).
- 566 [7] Mahtta, R., Mahendra, A. & Seto, K. C. Building up or spreading out? typologies of urban growth
567 across 478 cities of 1 million+. *Environmental Research Letters* **14**, 124077 (2019).
- 568 [8] Creutzig, F., Baiocchi, G., Bierkandt, R., Pichler, P.-P. & Seto, K. C. Global typology of urban
569 energy use and potentials for an urbanization mitigation wedge. *Proceedings of the national academy*
570 *of sciences* **112**, 6283–6288 (2015).
- 571 [9] Lamb, W. F., Creutzig, F., Callaghan, M. W. & Minx, J. C. Learning about urban climate solutions
572 from case studies. *Nature Climate Change* **9**, 279–287 (2019).
- 573 [10] Ostrom, E. Polycentric systems for coping with collective action and global environmental change.
574 *Global Environmental Change* **20**, 550–557 (2010).
- 575 [11] Priem, J., Piwowar, H. & Orr, R. OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues,
576 institutions, and concepts. *ArXiv* (2022). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.01833>.
- 577 [12] Xie, J., Girshick, R. & Farhadi, A. *Unsupervised deep embedding for clustering analysis*, 478–487
578 (PMLR, 2016).
- 579 [13] Guo, X., Gao, L., Liu, X. & Yin, J. Improved Deep Embedded Clustering with Local Structure
580 Preservation 1753–1759 (2017). URL <https://www.ijcai.org/proceedings/2017/243>.

- 581 [14] Oluchiri, S. O. Urban flooding in the cities of kisumu, mombasa, and nairobi, kenya: Causes,
582 vulnerability factors, and management. *African Journal of Empirical Research* **6**, 342–351 (2025).
- 583 [15] Gachahi, L. W. A comparative analysis of long-term variations of temperature and rainfall in rural
584 and urban areas, and their effects on the estimation of design storms in kenya (2016).
- 585 [16] Okaka, F. O. & Odhiambo, B. D. Health vulnerability to flood-induced risks of households in flood-
586 prone informal settlements in the coastal city of mombasa, kenya. *Natural Hazards* **99**, 1007–1029
587 (2019).
- 588 [17] van Staden, F. *Climate change impacts and adaptation strategies for tourism hotspots Mombasa and*
589 *Cape Town*, 138–151 (Routledge, 2020).
- 590 [18] Ojwang, R. O., Dietrich, J., Kasargodu Anebagilu, P., Beyer, M. & Rottensteiner, F. Rooftop
591 rainwater harvesting for mombasa: Scenario development with image classification and water resources
592 simulation. *Water* **9**, 359 (2017).
- 593 [19] Ogochukwu, C. G., Chioma, J.-N. A., Ogochukwu, O. F., Chukwudi, E. C. & Ogorchukwu, I. M.
594 Rapid spatial growth of cities and its planning implications for developing countries: a case study of
595 abuja, nigeria. *The Indonesian Journal of Geography* **54**, 313–320 (2022).
- 596 [20] Nachtigall, F., Wagner, F., Berrill, P. & Creutzig, F. Built environment and travel: tackling non-linear
597 residential self-selection with double machine learning. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport*
598 *and Environment* **140**, 104593 (2025).
- 599 [21] VandeWeghe, J. R. & Kennedy, C. A spatial analysis of residential greenhouse gas emissions in the
600 toronto census metropolitan area. *Journal of industrial ecology* **11**, 133–144 (2007).
- 601 [22] Adegun, O. B. Flood-related challenges and impacts within coastal informal settlements: a case from
602 lagos, nigeria. *International Journal of Urban Sustainable Development* **15**, 1–13 (2023).
- 603 [23] Khalil, H. A. E. E., Ibrahim, A., Elgendy, N. & Makhlof, N. Could/should improving the urban
604 climate in informal areas of fast-growing cities be an integral part of upgrading processes? cairo case.
605 *Urban climate* **24**, 63–79 (2018).
- 606 [24] Murthy, S. L. Land security and the challenges of realizing the human right to water and sanitation
607 in the slums of mumbai, india. *Health & Hum. Rts.* **14**, 61 (2012).
- 608 [25] Velumani, A., Saravanan, K., Kannadasan, T. & Ganesan, K. Design of temporary storage of
609 municipal solid waste and its impact on global warming—a case study. *Journal of Sustainable*
610 *Development* **2** (2009).
- 611 [26] Sangeetha, A. & Amudha, T. *A computational study on the effect of climatic parameters on air*
612 *pollution in coimbatore city*, 66–71 (IEEE, 2019).
- 613 [27] Nagpure, A. S., Tong, K. & Ramaswami, A. Socially-differentiated urban metabolism methodology
614 informs equity in coupled carbon-air pollution mitigation strategies: insights from three indian cities.
615 *Environmental Research Letters* **17**, 094025 (2022).
- 616 [28] Korade, M. S. & Dhorde, A. G. Trends in surface temperature variability over mumbai and ratnagiri
617 cities of coastal maharashtra, india. *Mausam* **67**, 455–462 (2016).

- 618 [29] Bhatia, A., Mathur, J. & Garg, V. Calibrated simulation for estimating energy savings by the use of
619 cool roof in five indian climatic zones. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy* **3** (2011).
- 620 [30] Weinstein, L., Rumbach, A. & Sinha, S. Resilient growth: Fantasy plans and unplanned developments
621 in india’s flood-prone coastal cities. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* **43**, 273–291
622 (2019).
- 623 [31] Awuor, C. B., Orindi, V. A. & Ochieng Adwera, A. Climate change and coastal cities: the case of
624 mombasa, kenya. *Environment and urbanization* **20**, 231–242 (2008).
- 625 [32] Kitha, J. & Lyth, A. Urban wildscapes and green spaces in mombasa and their potential contribution
626 to climate change adaptation and mitigation. *Environment and Urbanization* **23**, 251–265 (2011).
- 627 [33] Kithiia, J. & Lyth, A. in *Building resilience in east african cities: the spirit of “harambee”: Adaptive
628 capacity: the nexus between sustainability and climate change response* 273–285 (Routledge, 2013).
- 629 [34] Kithiia, J. & Dowling, R. An integrated city-level planning process to address the impacts of climate
630 change in kenya: The case of mombasa. *Cities* **27**, 466–475 (2010).
- 631 [35] Saba, M., Coronado-Hernández, O. E. & Gil, L. K. T. Energy efficiency in subtropical homes:
632 Replacing asbestos–cement roofs with sustainable alternatives. *Buildings* **14**, 4082 (2024).
- 633 [36] Stein, A. & Moser, C. Asset planning for climate change adaptation: lessons from cartagena, colombia.
634 *Environment and Urbanization* **26**, 166–183 (2014).
- 635 [37] Coronado-Hernández, Ó. E., Coronado-Hernandez, J. R. & Gatica, G. A practical methodology of
636 design of off-line reservoirs for reducing maximum water levels in urban channels. *Procedia Computer
637 Science* **175**, 441–446 (2020).
- 638 [38] Dadati, M. C. & D’Amico, M. *The Vivienda Azul-Verde: a rainwater harvesting system for El Pozón,
639 Cartagena de Indias*. Ph.D. thesis, Politecnico di Torino (2020).
- 640 [39] Wolff, E. & Ramírez-Lovering, D. in *Living with floods in informal settlements: compounding and
641 cascading risks in makassar, indonesia* 161–181 (Springer, 2022).
- 642 [40] French, M. A. *et al.* A planetary health model for reducing exposure to faecal contamination in urban
643 informal settlements: Baseline findings from makassar, indonesia. *Environment international* **155**,
644 106679 (2021).
- 645 [41] Ramsay, E. E. *et al.* Spatio-temporal development of the urban heat island in a socioeconomically
646 diverse tropical city. *Environmental Pollution* **316**, 120443 (2023).
- 647 [42] Ramsay, E. E. *et al.* Chronic heat stress in tropical urban informal settlements. *Isience* **24** (2021).
- 648 [43] Mesgar, M., Ramirez-Lovering, D. & El-Sioufi, M. Tension, conflict, and negotiability of land for
649 infrastructure retrofit practices in informal settlements. *Land* **10**, 1311 (2021).
- 650 [44] Mesgar, M. & Ramirez-Lovering, D. Informal land rights and infrastructure retrofit: A typology of
651 land rights in informal settlements. *Land* **10**, 273 (2021).
- 652 [45] Stanley, F. & Lisangan, E. A. Sistem dan simulasi deteksi banjir untuk peringatan dini diolah
653 memakai metode knn berbasis arduino. *TEMATIKA: Jurnal Penelitian Teknik Informatika dan
654 Sistem Informasi* 9–22 (2020).

- 655 [46] Handam, H. Environmental governance in handling flood problems in makassar city. *Journal of*
656 *Public Representative and Society Provision* **5**, 238–247 (2025).
- 657 [47] Damayanti, E., Sipato, W. D., Barkey, R. A. & Demallino, E. B. Strategi adaptasi dan pengendalian
658 dampak perubahan iklim kota makassar. *Jurnal Sosio Sains* **7**, 1–13 (2021).
- 659 [48] Burley Farr, K., Song, K., Yeo, Z. Y., Johnson, E. & Hsu, A. Cities and regions tackle climate change
660 mitigation but often focus on less effective solutions. *Communications earth & environment* **4**, 439
661 (2023).
- 662 [49] Seto, K. C., Fragkias, M., Güneralp, B. & Reilly, M. K. A meta-analysis of global urban land
663 expansion. *PloS one* **6**, e23777 (2011).
- 664 [50] Khanna, T. M. *et al.* A multi-country meta-analysis on the role of behavioural change in reducing
665 energy consumption and co2 emissions in residential buildings. *Nature Energy* **6**, 925–932 (2021).
- 666 [51] Prado, H. A. *et al.* Designing nature to be a solution for climate change in cities: A meta-analysis.
667 *Science of the Total Environment* **954**, 176735 (2024).
- 668 [52] Leck, E. The impact of urban form on travel behavior: A meta-analysis. *Berkeley Planning Journal*
669 **19** (2006).
- 670 [53] Howarth, C. & Painter, J. Exploring the science–policy interface on climate change: The role of the
671 IPCC in informing local decision-making in the UK. *Palgrave Communications* **2**, 1–12 (2016). URL
672 <https://www.nature.com/articles/palcomms201658>. Publisher: Palgrave.
- 673 [54] Callaghan, M. W., Minx, J. C. & Forster, P. M. A topography of climate change research. *Nature*
674 *Climate Change* **10**, 118–123 (2020).
- 675 [55] Callaghan, M. *et al.* Machine-learning-based evidence and attribution mapping of 100,000 climate
676 impact studies. *Nature climate change* **11**, 966–972 (2021).
- 677 [56] Montfort, S., Ingold, K., Fesenfeld, L., Repke, T. & Callaghan, M. The rising importance of
678 distributional barriers to climate mitigation policies. *Working Paper* (2024).
- 679 [57] Miake-Lye, I. M., Hempel, S., Shanman, R. & Shekelle, P. G. What is an evidence map? a systematic
680 review of published evidence maps and their definitions, methods, and products. *Systematic reviews*
681 **5**, 1–21 (2016).
- 682 [58] Nakagawa, S. *et al.* A new ecosystem for evidence synthesis. *Nature Ecology & Evolution* **4**, 498–501
683 (2020).
- 684 [59] James, K. L., Randall, N. P. & Haddaway, N. R. A methodology for systematic mapping in
685 environmental sciences. *Environmental evidence* **5**, 1–13 (2016).
- 686 [60] Rivero, I. M. *et al.* GHS-UCDB R2024A - GHS Urban Centre Database 2025 (2024). URL <http://data.europa.eu/89h/1a338be6-7eaf-480c-9664-3a8ade88cbcd>. Publisher: European Commission,
687 Joint Research Centre (JRC).
- 688 [61] Lizana, J. *et al.* Global gridded dataset of heating degree days and cooling degree days under three
689 climate scenarios: historical, 1.5° c and 2° c (2024).
- 690 [62] Solecki, W. *et al.* A conceptual framework for an urban areas typology to integrate climate change
691 mitigation and adaptation. *Urban Climate* **14**, 116–137 (2015).
- 692

- 693 [63] Strehl, A. & Ghosh, J. Cluster ensembles—a knowledge reuse framework for combining multiple
694 partitions. *Journal of machine learning research* **3**, 583–617 (2002).
- 695 [64] Fred, A. L. & Jain, A. K. Combining multiple clusterings using evidence accumulation. *IEEE*
696 *transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* **27**, 835–850 (2005).
- 697 [65] Vega-Pons, S. & Ruiz-Shulcloper, J. A survey of clustering ensemble algorithms. *International Journal*
698 *of Pattern Recognition and Artificial Intelligence* **25**, 337–372 (2011).
- 699 [66] Ariza, A. *et al.* Global decline of pelagic fauna in a warmer ocean. *Nature Climate Change* **12**,
700 928–934 (2022).
- 701 [67] Oke, J. B. *et al.* A novel global urban typology framework for sustainable mobility futures.
702 *Environmental Research Letters* **14**, 095006 (2019).
- 703 [68] Praene, J. P., Malet-Damour, B., Radanielina, M. H., Fontaine, L. & Riviere, G. Gis-based approach
704 to identify climatic zoning: A hierarchical clustering on principal component analysis. *Building and*
705 *Environment* **164**, 106330 (2019).
- 706 [69] Lu, Y., Li, H., Li, Y., Lin, Y. & Peng, X. A survey on deep clustering: from the prior perspective.
707 *Vicinagearth* **1**, 4 (2024).
- 708 [70] Li, L., Jamieson, K., DeSalvo, G., Rostamizadeh, A. & Talwalkar, A. Hyperband: A novel bandit-
709 based approach to hyperparameter optimization. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* **18**, 1–52
710 (2018).
- 711 [71] Lloyd, S. Least squares quantization in pcm. *IEEE transactions on information theory* **28**, 129–137
712 (1982).
- 713 [72] Xu, D. & Tian, Y. A comprehensive survey of clustering algorithms. *Annals of data science* **2**,
714 165–193 (2015).
- 715 [73] Fred, A. & Jain, A. K. *Evidence accumulation clustering based on the k-means algorithm*, 442–451
716 (Springer, 2002).
- 717 [74] Zhang, J., Wu, L., Cai, D., He, Y. & Wang, W. Deep ensemble clustering with partition alignment and
718 uniformity. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* (2021). Early Access.
- 719 [75] Alizadeh, R. & Bouguessa, M. *Improved deep embedded clustering with consistency and uncertainty*,
720 Vol. 36, 7407–7414 (2022).
- 721 [76] Kuhn, H. W. The hungarian method for the assignment problem. *Naval research logistics quarterly*
722 **2**, 83–97 (1955).
- 723 [77] Dimitriadou, E., Weingessel, A. & Hornik, K. An examination of indexes for determining the number
724 of clusters in binary data sets. *Psychometrika* **67**, 137–160 (2001).
- 725 [78] Caruana, R., Elhawary, M., Nguyen, N. & Smith, C. *Meta clustering*, 107–118 (IEEE, 2006).
- 726 [79] Boongoen, T. & Iam-On, N. Cluster ensembles: A survey of approaches with recent extensions and
727 applications. *Computer Science Review* **28**, 1–25 (2018).
- 728 [80] Fern, X. Z. & Brodley, C. E. *Solving cluster ensemble problems by bipartite graph partitioning*, 36
729 (2004).

- 730 [81] Mouillot, D. *et al.* Global correlates of terrestrial and marine coverage by protected areas on islands.
731 *Nature Communications* **11**, 4438 (2020).
- 732 [82] Pathirana, A. Small islands: Living laboratories revealing global climate and sustainable development
733 challenges. *Frontiers in Climate* **6**, 1445378 (2025).
- 734 [83] Sayre, R. *et al.* A new 30 meter resolution global shoreline vector and associated global islands
735 database for the development of standardized ecological coastal units. *Journal of Operational*
736 *Oceanography* **12**, S47–S56 (2019).
- 737 [84] Halterman, A. Mordecai: Full text geoparsing and event geocoding. *J. Open Source Softw.* **2**, 91
738 (2017).
- 739 [85] Pesaresi, M. *et al.* Advances on the global human settlement layer by joint assessment of earth
740 observation and population survey data. *International Journal of Digital Earth* **17**, 2390454 (2024).
- 741 [86] Repke, T. & Callaghan, M. Nacos-nexus: Nlp assisted classification, synthesis and online screening
742 with new and extended usage scenarios. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.04621* (2024).

Extended Data Figure A1 – Model choice validation with outcomes related to emissions, vulnerability, and health. We compute ANOVA percentages of variance accounted for by different clustering algorithms to validate whether the refinements introduced by the Deep Embedded Clustering pipeline (see Methods) yield substantively meaningful improvements in the cluster assignments. We compare these results against those from hierarchical clustering, K-means on the normalised feature space, and K-means on the embeddings. The evaluation focuses on outcomes related to 2020 emissions, vulnerability (floods, wildfire, and heat), and health.

Extended Data Figure A2 – Model performance and ensemble stability analysis. Model quality scores (Silhouette, Calinski–Harabasz, and Davies–Bouldin indices) for four clustering approaches—Deep Embedded Clustering, K-means on the embedded space, standard K-means, and hierarchical clustering highlight the consistently strong performance of the Deep Embedded Clustering model (in a). High Silhouette and Calinski–Harabasz values indicate more cohesive and well-separated clusters, whereas low Davies–Bouldin values indicate better cluster compactness and separation. Ensemble stability for the selected model with four clusters, quantified across 100 permutations (in b). We incrementally increase the number of runs contributing to the ensemble and compute the adjusted Rand index (ARI) between successive consensus solutions. Higher ARI values indicate closer agreement between ensembles, signalling that the consensus solution rapidly stabilises as additional runs are incorporated. This positive convergence pattern demonstrates that the ensemble clustering approach reliably yields a robust and reproducible consensus partition, even as new runs are added in different orders.

Extended Data Figure A3 – Cluster assignment probabilities and uncertainty diagnostics. We quantify the stability of the ensemble clustering by computing assignment probabilities across hard-aligned runs, based on the largest shared city membership across solutions. Panel (a) shows the distribution of assignment probabilities for each cluster, with violin plots indicating the density and box plots summarizing distributional moments. To flag uncertain assignments, we classify cities as mixed types when their assignment probability falls below $0.65 \times$ the cluster-specific median. This threshold was validated using our interactive web application (<https://cities-explorer.eubucco.com>), where cities with heterogeneous covariate profiles consistently display low assignment probabilities. A Wilcoxon rank-sum test indicates that mean assignment probabilities differ markedly between main-type and mixed-type cities; given the measurement uncertainty in GHSL UCDB, this test serves as a robustness diagnostic rather than a classical significance test. Overall, approximately 10% of cities are classified as mixed types, with Type 4 (mostly megacities) having the lowest and Type 3 (developed cities with predominantly mitigation priorities) the highest proportion of mixed assignments (b). Panel (c) shows the bootstrap distribution of the share of mixed-type cities, illustrating the stability of the threshold-based classification. The observed share (vertical line) lies well within the bootstrap distribution, indicating robustness of the mixed-type definition. Panel (d) reports the overlap of cluster membership by displaying, for each main cluster (horizontal axis), the probability that cities also belong to any secondary cluster (vertical axis). For example, cities in Type 4 show an average 0.32 probability of belonging to Type 3, reflecting where meaningful structural similarities exist between clusters.

Extended Data Figure A4 – Examples for each of the four types in the global urban typology (part 1). Development first (a-b), Mitigation first (c-d), Urban planning first (e-f), Mega all in (g-h) of cities. For each, we show the cities’ distribution characteristics (box plots and violin plots) alongside the value of that particular city (red dot) relative to the mean across all cities (dashed line). The number shows how much higher the cities’ value of a given characteristic is compared to all other cities. For instance, a value of two for population indicates that the city is twice as large as an average city. Additionally, the bar charts show the soft-assignment probability of our Deep Embedded Ensemble Clustering model to all types, meaning that a city can belong to several types to a variable degree.

Extended Data Figure A5 – Examples for each of the four types in the global urban typology (part 1). Development first (a-b), Mitigation first (c-d), Urban planning first (e-f), Mega all in (g-h) of cities. For each, we show the cities’ distribution characteristics (box plots and violin plots) alongside the value of that particular city (red dot) relative to the mean across all cities (dashed line). The number shows how much higher the cities’ value of a given characteristic is compared to all other cities. For instance, a value of two for population indicates that the city is twice as large as an average city. Additionally, the bar charts show the soft-assignment probability of our Deep Embedded Ensemble Clustering model to all types, meaning that a city can belong to several types to a variable degree.

Extended Data Figure A6 – Adaptation, mitigation and cross-cutting solutions in the ten case study examples. For each type, we computed the share of solutions mentioned in each of the solution domains.

Extended Data Figure A7 – CO₂ emissions. Contains p.c. emissions from the cities' from the ODIAC emissions database and the year 2020. We chose this year to limit the influence of the COVID pandemic. ODIAC emissions are not modelled and have higher resolution ($1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ grid) than alternatives like EDGAR.

Table A1 – Search terms

Urban keywords

("city" OR "cities" OR "urban" OR "municipal" OR "municipality" OR "cityscape" OR "metropolitan" OR "settlement" OR "settlements" OR "borough" OR "village" OR "megalopolis" OR "cosmopolitan" OR "conurban" OR "suburban" OR "hamlet" OR "precinct" OR "commune" OR "locality" OR "town" OR "periurban" OR "neighbourhood" OR "neighborhood")

Climate change

<urban keywords> AND ("climate" OR "climatic" OR "global warming")

Mitigation

<urban keywords> AND ("net zero" OR "net-zero" OR "zero carbon" OR "carbon neutral" OR "decarbonization" OR "decarbonisation" OR "carbon footprint" OR "carbon footprints" OR "decarbonise" OR "decarbonize" OR "decarbonising" OR "decarbonizing" OR "low-carbon" OR "low carbon" OR "low-emission" OR "low emission")

GHGs 1

<urban keywords> AND (((("carbon cycle" OR "carbon cycles" OR "carbon cycling" OR "carbon budget" OR "carbon budgets" OR "carbon flux" OR "carbon fluxes") AND (atmosphere OR atmospheric)) OR ("carbon emission" OR "carbon emissions")))

GHGs 2

<urban keywords> AND ("greenhouse gas" OR "greenhouse gases" OR "atmospheric carbon dioxide" OR "atmospheric CH4" OR "atmospheric CO2" OR "atmospheric methane" OR "atmospheric N2O" OR "atmospheric nitrous oxide" OR "carbon dioxide emission" OR "carbon dioxide emissions" OR "CH4 emission" OR "CH4 emissions" OR "CO2 emissions" OR "CO2 emission" OR dendroclimatology OR dendroclimatological OR ("emission of carbon dioxide" NOT nanotube) OR ("emissions of carbon dioxide" NOT nanotube) OR "emission of CH4" OR "emissions of CH4" OR "emission of CO2" OR "emissions of CO2" OR "emission of methane" OR "emissions of methane" OR "emission of N2O" OR "emissions of N2O" OR "emission of nitrous oxide" OR "emissions of nitrous oxide" OR "methane emission" OR "methane emissions" OR "N2O emission" OR "N2O emissions" OR "nitrous oxide emission" OR "nitrous oxide emissions")

Carbon dioxide removal

<urban keywords> AND ("sequestration of carbon" OR "sequestered carbon" OR "sequestering carbon" OR "sequestration of CO2" OR "sequestered CO2" OR "sequestering CO2" OR "CO2 capture" OR "CO2 storage" OR "CO2 sequestration" OR "CO2 sink" OR "CO2 sinks" OR "anthropogenic carbon" OR "capture of carbon dioxide" OR "capture of CO2" OR "CO2 abatement" OR "carbon sink" OR "carbon sinks" OR "carbon offset" OR "carbon sequestration" OR "carbon storage" OR "carbon capture")

Impacts and adaptation 1

<urban keywords> AND ("extreme weather" OR "heat stress" OR "sea level rise" OR "rising sea level" OR "rising sea levels" OR "heatwave" OR "extreme heat" OR "heat island" OR "heat islands" OR "glacier melt" OR "permafrost thaw" OR "adaptation planning" OR "adaptive capacity" OR "adaptive capacities" OR "resilience strategy" OR "impact resilient" OR "impact-resilient" OR "loss and damage" OR "nature-based solution" OR "nature-based solutions" OR "NbS" OR "ecosystem-based adaptation" OR "green infrastructure" OR "blue infrastructure" OR "green area" OR "green areas" OR "green roof" OR "green roofs" OR "green walls")

Impacts and adaptation 2

<urban keywords> AND (("stormwater" OR "tropical cyclone" OR "tropical cyclones" OR "hurricane" OR "hurricanes" OR "typhoon" OR "typhoons" OR "drought" OR "droughts" OR "flood" OR "floods" OR "flooding" OR "water scarcity" OR "water stress" OR "storm surge" OR "storm surges" OR "wildfire" OR "wildfires" OR "landslide" OR "landslides") AND ("extreme event" OR "severe weather events" OR "extreme natural events" OR "compounding weather events" OR "natural hazard" OR "natural disaster"))
